

**SHUMOLI-G'ARBIY QIZILQUM CHO'LIDA YAKKA HOLDA YASHOVCHI
(VESPIDAE: EUMENINAE) HAQIQIY ARILARI****Minajatdinova Zulkumar Nukusbayevna**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18185885>

Hozirgi vaqtda planetamizdagi haqiqiy arilar oilasi sistematik jihatdan Hymenoptera turkumiga birlashib hozirgi vaqtda 5000 ga yaqin ari turlari ma'lum, ammo ularning barchasida hayot shakllari bir xillikda emas. Asosan ikki: yakka va jamoa yashovchi arilar toifalariga ajraladi.

Biologik xilma-xillik holatini hisobga olish va nazorat qilish respublikaning barqaror rivojlanishiga erishish uchun o'simlik va hayvonot olamini monitoring qilish, ularni saqlash va oqilona foydalanish yo'nalishida parallel holatda doimiy amalga oshiriluvchi ikkita jarayonni nazarda tutadi. Haqiqiy arilar faunasini o'rganish ularning insonlarga tabiatga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatishi biologik ahamiyati muhim o'rin tutadi [1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7].

Qizilqum okrugi shimoli-g'arbda Quyi Amudaryo okrugi bilan, janubi-sharqda Quyi Zarafshon okrugi bilan, sharqda esa Toshkent-Mirzacho'l okrugi bilan chegaralanadi. Okrugning janubi-g'arbiy Turkmaniston, shimoli-sharqi Qozog'iston bilan bo'lgan davlat chegarasiga to'g'ri keladi. Qizilqum janubi-sharqdan shimoli-g'arbgga qarab pasayib boradi. Uning o'rtacha mutloq balandligi 200-300 m bo'lsa, janubi-sharqda 350-400 m, shimoli-g'arbda esa 90-100 m ga tushib qoladi. Qizilqum okrugida taqirlar kam bo'lib, ular marza qumlar orasidagi past joylarda uchraydi.

Taqirlar bahorda suv bilan qoplanib, yozga borib suv bug'lanib ketib, qurib usti qotib yorilib ketadi.

Tadqiqotlarimiz davomida materiallar 2022-2025 yillarda Shimoli g'arbiy Qizilqum cho'lining tabiiy va antropogen hududlaridan 20 ga yaqin koordinata nuqtalaridan yig'ildi.

Materiallarni yig'ishda V.B. Golub (2012) va ana'naviy uslub entomologik matrap, Merik plastik idishi, butalar, daraxt shoxlari, turar joy va xo'jalik binolar, pinset, fotoapparat va boshqalardan foydalanildi [3, 6].

Yakka holda yashovchi haqiqiy arilar kenja oilasining faunasini tadqiq qilish ishlari 2022-2025 yillar davomida Shimoli - g'arbiy Qizilqum cho'lining asosan so'g'orilmaydigan hududlarida olib borildi. Olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalarini tahlil qilish natijasida yakka holda yashovchi haqiqiy arilar Vespidae oilasi vakillari 1 ta kenja oila 12 avlodga mansub 13 tur va kenja turlari aniqlandi. Aniqlangan turlarning sistematik holati va faunistik malumotlari qo'yidagicha keltirildi.

Vespidae - oilasi**Eumeninae – kenja oilasi*****Antepipona de Saussure, 1855 – avlodi*****1. *Antepipona barrei* (Radoszkowski 1893) - turi.**

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 1♀, 1♂. (N 60.31852503795486, Y 42.18176934814461), 23.05.2024; 2♂. (N 60.48316909168007 Y 42.16171245390667) 23.05.2024.

Tarqalishi: Armonistona, Iron, Afg'oniston, Tojigiston, Qozog'iston, O'zbekiston.

Chlorodynerus Blüthgen, 1951 – avlodi.**2. *Chlorodynerus arenicola* (Kostylev, 1935) - turi.**

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: Shimoli - g'arbiy Qizilqum cho'li 1♀, 1♂. (N 61.39217334518785 E 42.72188305758066), 17.06.2023; 2♀, 3♂. (N 61.55176304318125 Y 42.63875081756731), 17.06.2023; 1♀. (N 60.37323335847554 Y 43.32803431146164), 14.06.2023; 3♀, 3♂. (N 60.24671619137703 Y 42.66406210078632) 14.06.2023.

Tarqalishi: Xitoy, Turkmaniston, Qazog'iston, O'zbekiston.

3. ***Chlorodynerus incisipes* (Kostylev, 1935) - turi.**

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 3♀, 2♂. (N 60.31852503795486, Y 42.18176934814461), 23.05.2024; 1♀, 4♂. (N 60.48316909168007 Y 42.16171245390667) 23.05.2024.

Tarqalishi: Iron, O'rto Osiyo.

Eumenes Latreille, 1802 – avlodi.

4. ***Eumenes sareptanus* André, 1884 turi.**

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 1♂. (N 59.97615033632654 Y 42.75565467164781), 23.05.2024; 2♀, 2♂. (N 60.36410266953806 Y 43.33710009351066) 23.05.2024.

Tarqalishi: Evropa, Rossiya, Turkiya, Turkmaniston, O'zbekiston, Qozog'iston.

Euodynerus Dalla Torre, 1904 - avlodnavlodi

5. ***Euodynerus strigatus* Radoszkowski 1893 turi.**

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 1♀, 4♂. (N 60.58620397439243 Y 42.61599660383926) 24.05.2022; 2♂. (N 61.13439408150873 Y 42.63137377097146) 24.05.2022; 2♀, 1♂. (N 59.97615033632654 Y 42.75565467164781), 23.05.2024.

Tarqalishi: O'rto Osiyo.

6. ***Euodynerus rufinus* Blüthgen, 1942 turi.**

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 1♂. (N 60.58620397439243 Y 42.61599660383926) 24.05.2022; 1♂. (N 61.13439408150873 Y 42.63137377097146) 24.05.2022; 2♀, 3♂. (N 59.97615033632654 Y 42.75565467164781), 23.05.2024.

Tarqalishi: Armeniya, Isroyl, Egitpit, Arabiya, Iron, Turkmaniston, Mongoliya, O'zbekiston.

Eustenancistrocerus Blüthgen, 1938 – avlod

7. ***Eustenancistrocerus askhabadensis* (Radoszkowski, 1886) turi.**

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 2♀, 4♂. (N 60.31852503795486, Y 42.18176934814461), 23.05.2024; 1♀, (N 60.43751340573701 Y 42.18856678120513) 23.05.2024; 3♀, 2♂. (N 60.48316909168007 Y 42.16171245390667) 15. 08.2024; 1♀, 1♂. (N 59.97615033632654 Y 42.75565467164781) 17. 08.2024.

Tarqalishi: Rossiya, Azerbaijan, Turkiya, Suriya, O'rto Osiyo.

Jucancistrocerus Blüthgen, 1938 – avlodi

8. ***Jucancistrocerus tachkendensis* (Dalla Torre, 1889) turi.**

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 3♂. (N 60.31852503795486, Y 42.18176934814461), 23.05.2024; 1♀, 4♂. (N 60.48316909168007 Y 42.16171245390667) 23.05.2024.

Tarqalishi: Xitoy, Afg'oniston, Pokiston, Turkmaniston, Qozog'iston, O'zbekiston.

Katamenes Meado Waldo, 1910 – avlodi

9. ***Katamenes dimidiatus* Brulle, 1832 turi.**

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 1♀, (N 65.83664082470418 Y 40.80121683620003), 17.05.2022; 4♀, (N 65.86463004539483 Y 40.97076299690683), 17.05.2022.

Tarqalishi: Evropa, Rossiya, Turkiya, Suriya, Iron, Mug‘iliston, Xitoy, Afg‘oniston, Pokiston, Qozog‘iston.

Odynerus Latreille, 1802 – avlodi.

10. ***Odynerus melanocephalus (Gmelin, 1790) turi.***

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: Аниқланган жойи ва вақти: 2♀, 3♂. (N 60.36410266953806 Y 43.33710009351066) 23.05.2022; 2♀, 2♂. (N 60.58620397439243 Y 42.61599660383926) 17.06.2023. 2♂. (N 61.13439408150873 Y 42.63137377097146) 24.05.2024.

Tarqalishi: Afrika, Qozog‘iston, Markaziy Osiyo, Siberiya, Iron.

Onychopterocheilus Bluthgen, 1955 – avlodi.

11. ***Onychopterocheilus fausti (Moravitz, 1873) turi.***

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 1♀, 1♂. (N 60.37323335847554 Y 43.32803431146164), 27.05.2022; 1♀, 3♂. (N 60.35942556971107 Y 43.34230314197199) 14.06.2023.

Tarqalishi: Markaziy Osiyo.

Paravespa Radoszkoowski, 1886 – avlod.

12. ***Paravespa quadricolor (Moravitz, 1885) turi.***

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 3♀, 3♂. (N 60.36724119128425 Y 43.3323281375823), 27.05.2022. 1♀, 2♂. (N 60.24671619137703 Y 42.66406210078632) 14.06.2023.

Tarqalishi: O‘rto Osiyo, Qozog‘iston.

Pseudepipona Saussure, 1856 – avlodi

13. ***Pseudepipona herrichii De Saussure, 1856 - turi.***

Aniqlangan joyi va vaqti: 4♀, 6♂. (N 60.36410266953806 Y 43.33710009351066) 23.05.2022; 2♀, 3♂. (N 60.58620397439243 Y 42.61599660383926) 17.06.2023. 2♂. (N 61.13439408150873 Y 42.63137377097146) 24.05.2024.

Tarqalishi: Rossia, Afrika, Turkiya, Suriya, Mongoliya, Xitoy, Amerika, Markaziy Osiyo.

Yakka holda yshovchi Eumeninae kenja oilasining avlodlar kesimida o‘rganilganda eng ko‘p *Chlorodynerus* va *Euodynerus* avlodlari har biri ikki turdan, bochqa *Antepipona*, *Eumenes*, *Pseudepipona*, *Jucancistrocerus*, *Eustenancistrocerus*, *Katamenes*, *Odynerus*, *Onychopterocheilus*, *Paravespa*, *Pseudepipona* avlodlari esa har biri 1 ta turdan tegishliligi aniqlandi.

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